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Role of Yoga in Speed of School Going Children

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Abstract

Speed is an essential element of performance, influencing everything from daily tasks to athletic performance. Nowadays, every human being need speed for his work in daily life or to perform in sports events. Today's era often gives preference to enhancing speed with the help of modern technologies and overlooks the potential of the ancient practice of Yoga. To know the effect of selected yoga practices on running speed, we did a 6-week study on school-going children. For this, a randomised controlled experiment was conducted with 60 students (from Saraswati Vidya Mandir Senior Secondary School, Aligarh, U.P.) aged 14 to 16 years old. They were all divided randomly into two equal groups of 30 each: the yoga and the control group. The yoga group went through selected yoga practices consisting of Gayatri Mantra, 10 Asanas, 3 Pranayamas, 1 Kriya and Yoga Nidra, while the control group continued with their usual school activities. To measure running speed, we used a 50-meter dash test. The results demonstrated significant improvements in running speed for the yoga group compared to the control group. This might be caused by muscle strength, power, cardiovascular fitness, flexibility, balance, foot mechanics and mental focus improvements. The findings suggest that yoga can be a valuable addition to training programs for school students who are seeking to enhance their running performance.

Keywords Yoga, Running Speed, Adolescents, Athletic Performance.

Introduction

Yoga is an ancient practice that originated in India and gained significant popularity worldwide for its physical, mental, and spiritual benefits. It is a mind-body fitness that combines muscular activity with an internally directed mindful focus on awareness of the self, the breath and energy. The yoga practices enhance the strength of the muscles and flexibility of the body, promote and improve the functioning of respiratory and cardiovascular systems, help in recovery and treatment of addiction, reduce stress, anxiety, depression, and chronic pain, improve sleep patterns and generally enhance wellbeing and quality of life (Yokesh,2019). Professional athletes are searching for yoga to improve their mental and physical performance. Skill in any game is a prerequisite in order to exhibit the top performance of the player. Simultaneously, it becomes highly impossible for any player to achieve such a level of performance without having a concrete base of fitness. (Hussain, et.al.,2011)

Running speed is defined as the rate at which an individual can cover a given distance in a specific amount of time. It is influenced by a variety of factors like psychological, physiological, and biomechanical factors.

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to study the effects of yogic practices on running speed in school going children.

Review of Literature

Physiologically, factors like running cadence can reduce spinal loading and impact forces, enhancing performance and potentially increasing speed (Rodacki et al., 2024). Physiological assessments, such as those involving electromyography, can provide insights into muscle function and balance, which are crucial for maintaining speed during dynamic activities (Phuaklikhit et al., 2024). Other factors like Maximal running speed (VMAX), heart rate at the second ventilatory threshold, and body composition significantly predict performance, with a notable relationship between metabolic cost and

running mechanics, such as contact and aerial times (Peyre Tartaruga et al., 2024). Key elements include VO₂ max, running economy, muscle fiber types, and fatigue levels, which all contribute to an individual's endurance and speed capabilities (Ogueta-Alday & García-López, 2016).

The scientist treats human foot as a simple lever of first type, in which the ankle acts as the fulcrum (as shown in figure). Force is provided by the calf muscle attached to the ankle to lift the foot. The key to mechanical advantage is the distance from the ankle to the point of ground contact- R . The gear ratio depends on the ratio of R to the distance from the muscle to the ankle, or r . A higher gear ratio, or larger R , means that the muscle contractions are slower but more powerful—for example, during an activity such as walking uphill. The foot's flexibility, especially of the toes, allows it to change R . When the foot rolls from heel to toe, R increases substantially, essentially changing gear from lower to higher. This ingenious mechanism maximizes the foot's functionality which helps enhancing its efficiency and power output.

Biomechanical factors like the individual-specific gait signatures (which include 3D kinematic and kinetic data) are essential for understanding how speed changes affect running dynamics (Winner et al., 2024). Ground reaction forces (GRFs) and muscle activity change with speed, where increased propulsive and vertical forces correlate with higher speeds, and variations in leg stiffness and stride characteristics also play critical roles in optimizing running economy (Jiang et al., 2024) (Willer et al., 2024) (Hooren et al., 2024). Other factors such as foot strike patterns, and spatio-temporal parameters are crucial, as they determine how effectively a runner can apply force to the ground relative to their body weight (Weyand, 2017) (Ogueta-Alday & García-López, 2016).

Psychological factors like the neuromuscular coordination of muscle groups during running, including the timing of limb movements and the activation of specific muscle fibres, play a significant role in optimising speed (Willer et al., 2024) (Vellucci & Beaudette, 2023). Understanding these factors can help develop targeted yogic training programs to improve running performance.

Yoga, with its emphasis on body awareness, flexibility, strength, and breath control, has the potential to influence several of these factors in adolescents positively. By addressing underlying physiological, biomechanical, and psychological components, yoga may contribute to improved running speed in this age group. The relationship between yoga and athletic performance has been a growing area of research, with increasing interest in its potential benefits for various sports. While studies directly examining the impact of yoga on running speed in adolescents are limited, existing research provides valuable insights into the potential mechanisms through which yoga can enhance running performance.

Power yoga and the vinyasa flow can significantly improve muscle strength and power which is essential for running speed. Studies have demonstrated that incorporating yoga into training programs can increase lower body strength, core stability, and explosive power in adolescent athletes (Ajayaghosh MV, 2018). Yoga practices involving rhythmic breathing and dynamic movements, can improve cardiovascular health. Research has shown that yoga can increase VO₂ max, lower resting heart rate, and enhance cardiovascular endurance (Dr. K. Divya, 2017, Mukesh Km. Mishra, 2015). Yoga is renowned for improving flexibility and balance, crucial for efficient running mechanics. Studies have found that yoga can increase joint range of motion, reduce muscle tension, and improve running form (Sanjiv S Patil, 2018, Shah Noman Md. Iftekhhar, 2017). Yoga has been shown to reduce stress and anxiety and improve mental focus, essential for optimal athletic performance. Studies have demonstrated that yoga can enhance concentration, reduce perceived exertion, and improve overall well-being in adolescent athletes (Khajuria et al, 2024).

While there may be fewer direct studies on yoga and running speed in adolescents, several studies have examined the effects of yoga on related factors that influence

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running performance. Given the potential benefits of yoga for physical and athletic development, this study aims to investigate the effects of selected yogic practices on school-going children's running speed. By examining the relationship between yoga and running performance in this age group, this research seeks to contribute to a growing body of evidence supporting the integration of yoga into adolescent physical education programs.

Methodology

A randomised controlled trial (RCT) was conducted to compare the effects of yogic practices between the group and the control group. The participants were randomly and equally assigned to both yoga and control group. This ensured that the groups were comparable at baseline.

Sixty male participants aged 14 to 16 were selected as samples for this study from Saraswati Vidya Mandir Senior Secondary School in the Aligarh district of Uttar Pradesh, INDIA. The yoga group participated in a 6-week yoga program, which consisted of 5 days per week, while the control group continued with their usual physical and school activity routines. Each yoga session was 60 minutes long and was held in the morning, from 7:30 AM to 8:30 AM, during September and October 2023. The average temperature in Aligarh during these months was approximately $28^{\circ}\text{C} \pm (82^{\circ}\text{F} \pm)$, with potential variations.

The yoga program focused on asanas, pranayama, kriyas and yoga Nidra techniques known to benefit running speed, which included Loosening/ warming up activities, Gayatri mantra recitation, performing Tadasana, Trikonasana, Paschimottanasana, Ardha-Matsyendrasana, Sarvangasana, Halasana, Chakrasana, Bhujangasana, Shalabhasana, Dhanurasana, Kapalbhathi, Anulom Vilom, Brahmari, modified Trataka and Yoga Nidra. Shavasana and Makarasana were also performed to provide relaxation between the two activities. This programme was constructed with the help of consultation with the supervisor, previous literature and other yoga experts. Qualified yoga instructors led the yoga sessions.

Running speed was assessed using a standardised 50-meter dash test before and after the 6-week yoga program. Data was collected using a stopwatch (standardised measurement equipment). For the 50-meter dash test, participants stood behind a starting line and sprinted as fast as possible to the finish line. Time was recorded using a stopwatch. Each participant was given sufficient time for a proper warm-up to prepare their body for the run. After the warm-up, they performed only one trial of the 50-meter dash. Their time was recorded immediately after running.

A Paired sample t-test was used to compare statistically the data of pre and post-test. Effect size was calculated to quantify the magnitude of the difference in running speed between the groups. The level of significance was considered at 0.05.

Ethical Considerations

In our study, we ensured that the welfare and rights of humanity remained protected. We ensured that all participants were made entirely aware of the purpose of the study, including procedures, risks, and benefits. To ensure confidentiality, access to data was limited and information further anonymised. Participation was voluntary; subjects could withdraw participation at any time without penalty or loss. The precautionary measures taken to prevent causing distress and keeping the participants safe were apart from these. The goal was to know the effect of our designed yoga programme on running speed in teenagers while keeping the risks low and ensuring everyone was treated fairly.

Analysis

Table 1: Summary of Speed statistics for Yoga and Control group (time in seconds)

Group	Data type	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	T value	P value
Yoga	Pre	8.45	1.07	0.58	6.16	<0.001
	Post	7.86	0.84			
Control	Pre	8.48	1.02	0.35	5.08	0.00002
	Post	8.13	1.09			

(Tabulated t-value = 2.045, Level of significance = 0.05, df=29)

Figure 1: Graphical Presentation of both groups means

Inference

In this study, we did a statistical analysis to observe the effect of our yoga program on running speed in teenagers. After applying a paired sample t-test over the data the yoga group t-value was (6.16) with a p-value of (< 0.001), which indicates that the running speed improves after the yoga program. The control group showed a t-value of (5.08) and a p-value of (0.00002), which also indicated a significant change in running speed.

We then compared the obtained t-values to the tabulated t-value of about (2.045) at the significance level of (0.05) with $df = 29$. Since both the calculated t-values were greater than the tabulated value, we rejected the null hypothesis for both groups; that was, there will be no significant difference in running speed.

But the effect size showed tiny differences between the groups before the intervention. Then, it increased to a moderate level after the intervention. The effect size for the pre-test is very small, with Cohen's $d = 0.03$, Glass's $\delta = 0.028$, and Hedges' $g = 0.03$. Effect size increased to a moderate level after the intervention, with Cohen's $d = 0.28$, Glass's $\delta = 0.32$, and Hedges' $g = 0.28$. Therefore, the yoga program may have assisted the experimental group in improving running speed compared to the control group.

The results of this study show that yoga helped yoga group participants to run faster in compare of control group. So, we can say that adding yoga practices can enhance the running speed of young people and improve their performance. Such findings help in understanding how yoga might positively affect the physical skills of youngsters

Result and Discussion

This research aimed to investigate the impact of a 6-week yoga program on the running speed of adolescent boys. The study's findings demonstrate that regular yoga practice can significantly improve running speed in this age group.

The figure shows that when the heel strikes the ground and the calf muscle absorbs the shock, the gear ratio is at its lowest. However, as the foot shifts forward toward the toes, the ratio rises significantly. The moment arm R increases nearly twenty times. This shifting to a higher gear (towards toe) enables the calf muscles to contract more slowly, resulting in greater power output which helps to increase running speed.

The body relaxes and remains comfortable when holding the final posture, various muscles, tendons, and joints are tensed smoothly and pleasantly, and asanas are performed passively, with no sense of effort, which positively contributes to the improvement of performance in the 50-meter dash test. Consequently, in practice of asana, postural reflex promotes internal awareness, relaxes the mind, and conditioning through the functional axis of cerebellum-hypothalamus. Both parasympathetic and sympathetic nervous systems are now working again and balanced. This is via interceptors such as muscles, spindles, and tendons that start feeding the brain with feelings about the body's position, movement, and balance. The higher center of the cortex does not interfere with the proprioceptors. However, the lower brain intervenes unconsciously - one that understands and unconsciously integrates information during practice of asana.

The yoga group, which received yoga training, experienced a notable reduction in 50-meter dash times compared to the control group. This is consistent with previous research suggesting that yoga can enhance athletic performance. The improvements in

running speed observed in the present study can be attributed to several factors. Yoga has been shown to improve muscle strength and power (Ajayagosh MV, 2018; Shirley Telles, 2014; Sunil Rayat, 2015), which are essential for running performance. Additionally, yoga can enhance cardiovascular fitness (Dr K. Divya, 2017; Tarak Nath Pramanik et al., 2024), flexibility and balance (Rajwinder Kaur, 2024; Shah Noman Md. Iftekhhar, 2017; Sunil Rayat, 2015). These improvements in physical fitness can contribute to faster running times.

The findings of this study align with previous research demonstrating the benefits of yoga for athletic performance. Yoga can have positive psychological effects, such as reducing stress and anxiety, which can enhance athletic performance. By improving mental focus and reducing distractions, yoga can help athletes perform at their best (Khajuria et al, 2024).

At last the results of this study suggest that yoga can be a valuable addition to training programs for adolescent school students/athletes seeking to improve their running speed. By incorporating yoga into their routines, school students/athletes may experience enhanced physical fitness, improved mental well-being, and better running performance.

Conclusion

The above literature suggests that yoga can impact positively on running speed in adolescents by addressing various physiological, biomechanical, and psychological factors. By improving muscle strength, power, cardiovascular fitness, flexibility, balance, foot mechanics and mental focus, yoga can help to enhance running performance and optimise athletic potential.

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